



*Supplemental Figure S1.* Target ear tag placement diagram. Tags ideally would be placed within the inner third of the ear, closest to the head, between the ribs.



Supplemental Figure S2. Proportion of tissue types present at the front right ear at each week of age (0-22 wk). Calves were ear tagged at 2 d of age and ear tag wounds were scored weekly, beginning on d 4 of life (wk 0), beginning on d 4 of life (wk 0). Brighter colors indicate a higher proportion of calves (sample size noted across the top) had that tissue type present at that week, while darker colors indicate a lower proportion of calves.



Supplemental Figure S3. Proportion of tissue types present at the front left ear at each week of age (0-22 wk). Calves were ear tagged at 2 d of age and ear tag wounds were scored weekly, beginning on d 4 of life (wk 0). Brighter colors indicate a higher proportion of calves (sample size noted across the top) had that tissue type present at that week, while darker colors indicate a lower proportion of calves.



*Supplemental Figure S4.* Proportion of tissue types present at the back right ear at each week of age (0-22 wk). Calves were ear tagged at 2 d of age and ear tag wounds were scored weekly, beginning on d 4 of life (wk 0). Brighter colors indicate a higher proportion of calves (sample size noted across the top) had that tissue type present at that week, while darker colors indicate a lower proportion of calves.



Supplemental Figure S5. Proportion of tissue types present at the back left ear at each week of age (0-22 wk). Calves were ear tagged at 2 d of age and ear tag wounds were scored weekly, beginning on d 4 of life (wk 0). Brighter colors indicate a higher proportion of calves (sample size noted across the top) had that tissue type present at that week, while darker colors indicate a lower proportion of calves.



Supplemental Figure S6. Proportion of tissue types present at the front of the ear at each week of age (0-22 wk) for calves who were tagged on the rib. Calves were ear tagged at 2 d of age and ear tag wounds were scored weekly, beginning on d 4 of life (wk 0). Brighter colors indicate a higher proportion of ears (left and/or right ears for all calves included in that week's sample, noted across the top) had that tissue type present at that week, while darker colors indicate a lower proportion of ears.



Supplemental Figure S7. Proportion of tissue types present at the front of the ear at each week of age (0-22 wk) for calves who were not tagged on the rib. Calves were ear tagged at 2 d of age and ear tag wounds were scored weekly, beginning on d 4 of life (wk 0). Brighter colors indicate a higher proportion of ears (left and/or right ears for all calves included in that week's sample, noted across the top) had that tissue type present at that week, while darker colors indicate a lower proportion of ears.



Supplemental Figure S8. Proportion of tissue types present at the back of the ear at each week of age (0-22 wk) for calves who were tagged on the rib. Calves were ear tagged at 2 d of age and ear tag wounds were scored weekly, beginning on d 4 of life (wk 0). Brighter colors indicate a higher proportion of ears (left and/or right ears for all calves included in that week's sample, noted across the top) had that tissue type present at that week, while darker colors indicate a lower proportion of ears.



Supplemental Figure S9. Proportion of tissue types present at the back of the ear at each week of age (0-22 wk) for calves who were not tagged on the rib. Calves were ear tagged at 2 d of age and ear tag wounds were scored weekly, beginning on d 4 of life (wk 0). Brighter colors indicate a higher proportion of ears (left and/or right ears for all calves included in that week's sample, noted across the top) had that tissue type present at that week, while darker colors indicate a lower proportion of ears.